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Research Article

**NEW VALIDATED EXTRACTIVE SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC
METHOD FOR THE DETERMINATION OF RUFINAMIDE IN
BULK AND ITS PHARMACEUTICAL DOSAGE FORM****¹P. Jagadeesh, ²U. Srikanth, ³M. M. Eswarudu*, ⁴P. Srinivasa Babu, ⁵Sk. Aneesh, ⁶P.S.H. R. Khan, ⁷S. Sai Pooja, ⁸K. Naga Rani**¹Department of Pharmaceutical Analysis, Vignan Pharmacy College, Vadlamudi (V), Chebrolu (M), Guntur (Dist), Andhra Pradesh, India. 522213.

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Abstract:

A simple, precise, selective and affordable spectrophotometric method has been developed for the determination of Rufinamide in its bulk and pharmaceutical dosage form. The method was based on ion-pair complex formation between the drug and anionic dye i.e. Bromothymol blue in acidic medium (pH 2.0-4.0). The coloured complex formed was quantitatively extracted into chloroform and measured wavelength at 416.5 nm. Beer's law was obeyed in the concentration range of 10-60 µg/ml with correlation coefficient (n=6) ≥ 0.997 . The stoichiometry of the complexes formed between drug and dye was 1:1 ratio, as determined by job's method of continuous variation. The association constant (Ka) of the ion-pair complexes formed was evaluated using Benesi-Hildebrand equation. Extraction procedure at various pH was measured and maximum absorbance was shown at pH 4.0. The developed method was validated according to ICH [Q2 (R1)] guidelines. This method has been successfully applied for the assay of drug in pharmaceutical formulations. No interference was observed from pharmaceutical adjuvants.

Keywords: Rufinamide, Bromothymol blue, Chloroform, Ion- pair complex, UV- Visible spectrophotometer, Validation.

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INTRODUCTION:

Epilepsy is a very common disorder, characterized by seizures, which take various forms and result from episodic neuronal discharges, the form of the seizure depending on the part of the brain affected. Epilepsy affects 0.5-1% of the population. Often, there is no recognizable cause, although it may develop after brain damage, such as trauma, stroke, infection or tumour growth, or other kinds of neurological disease, including various inherited neurological syndromes [1].

Rufinamide (RFN), chemically known as 1-[(2, 6-Di fluoro phenyl) methyl]-1H-1, 2, 3-triazole-4-carboxamide (Fig.1), is a triazole

derivative structurally unrelated to any currently marketed antiepileptic drug [2]. Rufinamide was granted orphan drug status for adjunctive treatment of patients with Lennox–Gastaut syndrome in October 2004, received its marketing authorization in Europe in January 2007, and was approved by the FDA in December in 2008 for adjunctive treatment of seizures associated with Lennox–Gastaut syndrome for children 4 years or older and for adults [3-4]. The mechanism of action of Rufinamide involves stabilization of the sodium channel inactive state, effectively keeping the ion channels closed. It is believed to prolong the refractory period of voltage-dependent sodium channels, making neurons less likely to fire [5].

Figure 1: Chemical Structure of Rufinamide

Literature survey revealed that a few Spectrophotometric [6-9], HPLC [10-13] methods were reported earlier for the determination of RFN in bulk and pharmaceutical dosage forms. Aim of the present work to development of simple, sensitive, accurate and precise extractive Spectrophotometric method using Chromogenic reagent i.e. Bromothymol Blue. The proposed method was based on ion-pair complex formation between the RFN and Bromothymol Blue. The proposed methods were applied to the determination of RFN in tablets, and no interference from common excipients in tablets was observed in the assay. The developed method was validated according to ICH guidelines [14- 15].

MATERIAL AND METHODS:**Equipments and Apparatus:**

All Spectrophotometric measurements were carried out using an Elico, model SL-159 (Mumbai, India) UV- Visible spectrophotometer. The cells used for absorbance measurements were 1-cm matched quartz cells. Samples were weighed by using Shimadzu electronic weighing balance (Tokyo, Japan), BL 220 H model. pH was adjusted by using pH meter (Elico model LI 120) Hot air oven (Vision Lab Equipments) and all reagents are prepared in borosil glassware.

Chemicals/Reagents:

All the chemicals used were of analytical reagent grade and used as received. All the solutions were prepared a fresh daily in double distilled water. Bromothymol Blue and Dimethyl sulfoxide (Qualigens fine chemicals, Mumbai, India), Potassium dihydrogen Phosphate, Ethanol and Ortho phosphoric acid (Thermo Fisher Scientific India Pvt. Ltd, Mumbai, India) were received and used. Spectrophotometric grade chloroform (Merck Specialities Pvt. Ltd, Mumbai, India) was used for the extraction of the ion-pair complex. Pharmaceutical grade Rufinamide was obtained as a gift sample from Hetero Drug Pvt Ltd, Hyderabad, India. Commercial dosage forms of Rufinamide such as Banzel- 200 mg tablets (Eisai pharmaceuticals ltd., India) were purchased from a local pharmacy store.

Preparation of standard stock solution:

Standard solution of Rufinamide (0.1 mg/ml) was prepared by accurately weighed 10 mg of drug dissolved in 5 ml of Dimethyl sulfoxide and then diluted up to the mark in a 100 mL volumetric flask with distilled water.

Preparation of Bromothymol Blue reagent (0.01% w/v):

Accurately weighed 10 mg of Bromothymol blue powdered dye transferred into a 100 ml clean dry

volumetric flask and dissolved in 100 ml of 50% ethanol[16].

Preparation of Potassium dihydrogen Phosphate buffer solution (0.2M):

Dissolved 0.504 grams of disodium hydrogen phosphate and 0.301 grams of potassium dihydrogen phosphate in sufficient water to produce 100 ml and adjusted the pH to 4.0 with diluted o- phosphoric acid [17].

Method development:

The ion-pair complex is a special form of molecular complex resulting from two oppositely charged ions extractable into organic solvents from aqueous phase at suitable pH. Initially, the field of physical chemistry has investigated the ion pair complex formation which is now being applied widely for the chemical as well as pharmaceutical analysis. By using an anionic dye as a reagent and organic solvent as an extractant the quantification of several

pharmaceutical compounds that possess basic moieties (secondary or tertiary amino group) is done by the ion-pair extractive spectrophotometry. As Bromothymol blue as Chromogenic reagent; it involves in the formation of ion pair complex. Because of this nature, they contribute to simple and rapid Spectrophotometric determination of many organic compounds of pharmaceutical significance. The results obtained in the proposed method were based on the tendency of the RFN to form chloroform extractable ion-pair complex with Bromothymol blue under experimental conditions. The positively charged primary nitrogen of RFN in acid medium is likely to attract the negatively charged part of Bromothymol blue and form an ion-pair complex held together through electrostatic attraction. RFN-BTB ion-pair complex showed maximum absorbance at 416.5 nm. The RFN- BTB ion-pair complex was stable for 60 minutes at room temperature. The proposed reaction schemes are presented in Fig.2.

Figure 2: proposed reaction scheme for formation of RFN-BTB ion pair Complex:

(I) Rufinamide, (II) Bromothymol blue, (III) RFN-BTB ion pair complex.

Methodology:

Into a series of 250 mL capacity separating funnels, aliquots of working standard RFN 2 ml of each concentration (10 -60 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) solutions were transferred. Then, to each separating funnel 2 mL of BTB solution and 6 ml of potassium dihydrogen phosphate buffer and 10 ml of chloroform (1:1:3:5) were transferred to each separating funnel. The funnels were shaken vigorously for 5 minutes and funnels were allowed to stand for 5 minutes the clear separation of the two phases. The chloroform

phase was extracted and collected into a 25 mL volumetric flask; absorption spectrums of the resulting solutions were determined using a spectrophotometer and the absorbances of the chloroform phase were measured at 416.5 nm against reagent blank. The amount of the drug in the unknown sample solution was computed either from the corresponding calibration graph or from the regression equation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:**Analytical Method Validation:**

Method validation was performed by following the International Conference on Harmonization (ICH) guideline for analytical method validation [14-15]. Under the experimental conditions described, the Beer's law was obeyed over the concentration ranges of 10- 60 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ for this method. The linear regression analysis using the method of least square

was made to assess slope, intercept and regression coefficient. High values of the regression coefficient and the small values of the intercept of the regression equation proved the linearity of the calibration curve. The values of limit of detection and limit of quantitation reveal the high sensitivity of the proposed method. Results were shown in the Table 1 and the linearity curve of RFN with BTB complex was shown in Fig.3.

Table 1: Linearity and sensitivity data

Parameter	Magnitude
Beer's law limit	10- 60 $\mu\text{g/mL}$
Regression equation($Y= mx + c$) [§]	$y = 0.014x + 0.107$
Slope (m)	0.014
Intercept(c)	0.107
Regression coefficient (r^2)	0.997
LOD ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	3.92
LOQ ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	11.90

[§] $Y = mx + c$, where Y is the absorbance, X is concentration in $\mu\text{g/mL}$, c is intercept and m is slope.

Figure 3: Linearity curve of Rufinamide

The accuracy and precision of the proposed method was assessed by determining the concentration of RFN at three different concentration levels (low, medium and high) within one day. Mean recoveries

obtained by intraday assay method was calculated and are summarized in Table 2. The results of the assays are acceptable and can be considered to be very reasonable.

Table 2: Accuracy data of Rufinamide

S.No.	µg/ml added	µg/ml found	% recovery	Mean % recovery
1	20	16.92	84.61	81.570
2	20	16.05	80.28	
3	20	15.96	79.80	
1	40	34.81	87.03	90.428
2	40	37.67	94.19	
3	40	36.02	90.05	
1	60	54.39	90.65	91.124
2	60	54.93	91.56	
3	60	54.69	91.15	

The intraday and inter day precision studies were determined by performing six independent analyses at 30 µg/mL concentration. The standard deviations, relative standard deviation were calculated and

results were summarized in Table 3 and Table 4. Results of the study are acceptable and can be considered to be very reasonable.

Table 3: Intra- day precision data of proposed method

S.No.	Concentration (µg/ml)	Absorbance		
		Morning	Afternoon	Evening
1	40	0.724	0.719	0.716
2	40	0.721	0.72	0.719
3	40	0.728	0.723	0.721
4	40	0.718	0.714	0.712
5	40	0.722	0.719	0.714
6	40	0.723	0.718	0.717
Average	-	0.722	0.719	0.716
S.D	-	0.003	0.002	0.003
%R.S.D	-	0.460	0.407	0.456

Table 4: Inter-day precision data of proposed method

S.No.	Concentration (µg/ml)	Absorbance		
		Day 1	Day 2	Day 3
1	30	0.547	0.543	0.538
2	30	0.542	0.535	0.542
3	30	0.543	0.529	0.541
4	30	0.548	0.536	0.538
5	30	0.551	0.539	0.529
6	30	0.539	0.54	0.532
Average	-	0.545	0.537	0.536
S.D	-	0.004	0.004	0.005
%R.S.D	-	0.812	0.904	0.954

For the assessment of method robustness, some experimental parameters were interchanged. The analysis was performed at the deliberately varied experimental conditions by taking two different wavelengths (± 2 nm) and concentrations of RFN (BTB20 µg/mL). The standard deviations, relative

standard deviation was calculated and is summarized in Table 5. The ability remained unaffected by small deliberate variations. Results of the study are acceptable and can be considered to be very reasonable.

Table 5: Robustness studies data of Rufinamide with proposed method

S.No.	Concentration (µg/ml)	Absorbance		
		At 414.5nm	At 416.5 nm	At 418.5nm
1	20	0.412	0.416	0.422
2	20	0.415	0.421	0.425
3	20	0.418	0.422	0.426
4	20	0.41	0.424	0.432
5	20	0.421	0.428	0.436
6	20	0.422	0.432	0.437
Average	-	0.416	0.424	0.429
S.D	-	0.004	0.005	0.006
%R.S.D	-	0.116	0.119	0.144

Application of the proposed methods to tablet dosage forms:

The proposed method was applied to the quantitation of Rufinamide in tablet dosage form. Tablets were purchased from a local pharmacy store. Twenty tablets were accurately weighed and finely powdered. A powdered amount equivalent to 10 mg was dissolved in 5 ml of Dimethyl sulfoxide and diluted up to 100 mL with distilled water and sonicated for 10 minutes. The solution was filtered using Whatman

No. 1 filter paper. From the filtrate 1mL was transferred into a 100 mL volumetric flask and made up to volume with distilled water. This solution was further diluted appropriately to get 20, 40 and 60 µg/mL concentrations for determination. The results shown in Table 6, suggest that the method was suitable for the determination of RFN with good accuracy and precision. The excipients in the dosage forms do not interfere in the assay procedure.

Table 6: Assay results of proposed method

Drug name	Formulation	Label Claim	Amount Found	% Assay
Rufinamide	Banzel	200 mg/tablet	196.89 mg/tablet	98.745

CONCLUSION:

The spectroscopic method was developed for the quantitation of Rufinamide using Chromogenic reagent Bromothymol blue. The developed method was validated as per ICH guidelines. It was observed that all validation parameters such as linearity, accuracy, precision, selectivity, sensitivity and robustness convey the predetermined acceptance criteria. Thus, it has been concluded that the proposed method re-validated for the routine analysis of the drug in bulk and its tablet dosage form and found all results were within the limits.

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